

occurrence on rice glumes in India.

The fungus produces hyaline, caenocytic mycelium. Conidiophores are short and simple. Conidia are dark and 5-celled, with hyaline and pointed-end

cells having 2–3 hyaline apical appendages. Size of conidia is 30–35 × 7–10 µm with appendages 20–35 µm long.

During pathogenicity tests, mycelial

bits of the fungus were prepared from 7-d-old culture and sprayed on rice grain at different stages. The milk stage was found to be most susceptible to fungal infection (see table). □

Effect of grain spotting on rice quality

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Grain spotting is caused by several microorganisms (*Trichoconis* spp., *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Pyricularia oryzae*, *Aspergillus* spp., *Alternaria padwickii*, *Curvularia* spp., etc.).

Symptoms (distinct black dots, sometimes brown blackish blotches) vary with the degree of infection.

We sampled grain lots of 21 varieties and measured grain spotting incidence.

Twenty-five healthy and 25 infected seeds of each variety were selected at random, dehusked, and the husk and grain weighed.

Ten healthy and 10 infected seeds were dehusked and the grains placed in 15- × 1-cm test tubes with 10 ml water each tube. Grain volume was measured. The tubes were placed in a 500-ml beaker with 200 ml water, heated for 30

Loss to grain spotting, Bilaspur, India.

Variety	Infection (%)	Loss (g) in husk weight	Difference in 1000-grain weight (g)	Cooking expansion difference (ml)
Jaya	6.2	0.26	1.79	0.12
Ratna	7.3	0.18	3.27	0.12
Bd 200	3.4	0.11	2.01	0.00
R-35-2752	9.1	0.51	0.78	2.19
BPT1235	6.2	0.31	4.33	1.95
Surekha	4.6	0.21	1.80	0.48
RP9-4	5.4	0.12	2.84	0.24
Saket-4	5.8	0.30	3.62	1.09
IR36	10.3	0.30	0.26	0.73
Chatri	10.4	0.53	0.07	1.09
Mahsuri	1.6	0.11	3.44	0.36
IET4094	5.2	0.28	5.96	1.09
R-2384	11.7	0.06	3.94	0.36
Phalguna	4.1	0.13	3.75	0.45
Pankaj	4.0	0.10	2.09	0.00
Kranti	6.9	0.17	0.20	0.61
Pusa	7.3	0.11	3.99	0.61
IET3273	11.5	0.39	0.65	0.36
Jagriti	4.7	0.27	1.70	0.24
Garima	4.5	0.12	1.86	0.36
Patel 85	4.8	0.21	2.73	0.73

min, and grain volume after cooking measured.

All varieties showed grain spotting (see table). Infected seeds weighed less

than healthy seeds. Infected husk also weighed less. Healthy grains expanded more than spotted grains with cooking. □

Distribution of rice seedling damping-off in Bangladesh

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Rice seedling damping-off caused by *Achlya* sp. was first identified in Bangladesh in 1978. The disease is soil borne and is disseminated through both soil and water. The pathogen affects seeds or young seedlings during the winter (Nov–Feb). The fungus forms a gray/ brown/ black-colored tangled mass of hyphae covering the surface of the infected seeds.

During 1978, severe seed or seedling damage occurred in the seedbed at the BRRI farm. Almost all rice varieties or

Severity of rice seedling damping-off in 11 districts of Bangladesh, winter, 1987.

District	Seedbeds affected (%)	Severity (0-9 scale ^a)
Bogra	30	5–7
Comilla	25	5–7
Chittagong	25	5–7
Dinajpur	40	5–7
Gazipur	30	5–9
Jamalpur	70	5–9
Mymensingh	30	5–7
Pabna	30	5–7
Rajshahi	40	3–5
Rangpur	60	3–9
Tangail	20	3–5

^a 0 = no incidence, 3 = 11–20% damage, 4 = 21–30% damage, 5 = 31–40% damage, 6 = 41–50% damage, 7 = 51–60% damage, 8 = 61–70% damage, and 9 = 81–100% damage.

lines sown were affected, with up to 80% seed or seedling mortality.

We surveyed the distribution and intensity of the disease in different districts during Jan 1987. The disease was prevalent in all 11 districts visited, with damage as high as 70% in seedbeds kept submerged during and after sowing (see table). □

Relationship between tungro transmission by individual *Nephotettix virescens*, mode of feeding, and life span

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A green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* colony collected from

Transmission of RTBV, RTSV, and RTBV +RTSV on IR54, IR36, and TN1 by GLH, area of acidic and basic honeydew excreted during inoculation feeding, and survival of GLH on the respective cultivars. IRRI, 1986.

Koronadal, South Cotabato, and reared on TN1 for 5-6 overlapping generations was used in this study. About 3-4 d after molting, adult GLH were given 4-d acquisition access to plants infected with both rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical viruses (RTSV). The GLH then were tested individually on IR36, IR54, and TN1 for virus transmission, feeding behavior during inoculation feeding, and survival on seedlings.

Feeding behavior was monitored by the reaction of honeydew spots on bromocresol-green treated filter paper discs. Blue color spots (basic honeydew) indicates phloem feeding and orange or brown color spots (acidic honeydew) indicates xylem feeding. Inoculated plants were indexed by latex serology. After inoculation feeding, each GLH was caged on about 3-wk-old plants of the respective cultivars to determine life span.

Leafhoppers fed on both phloem and xylem on all test varieties. They excreted less basic honeydew on GLH-resistant IR36 and IR54, survived fewer days, and transmitted viruses at lower rates (see figure). On susceptible TN1, the GLH excreted more basic honeydew, survived longer, and transmitted viruses at higher rates.

There was a significant correlation between percent virus transmission and, the average areas of basic honeydew spots, and the average life span of GLH on the test varieties. However, there was

Transmission of RTBV and RTSV on 3 cultivars by individual GLH and their feeding behavior during inoculation access.^a IRRI, 1987.

Cultivar	GLH tested (no.)	Transmissions (no.) by GLH	GLH (no.) that fed on		
			Phloem	Phloem and xylem	Xylem
IR36	30	RTBV+RTSV	10	7	3
		RTBV	7	5	2
		RTSV	1	1	0
		None	12	1	11
IR54	30	RTBV+RTSV	3	2	1
		RTBV	9	2	7
		RTSV	0	0	0
		None	18	3	15
TN1	30	RTBV+RTSV	18	16	2
		RTBV	6	6	0
		RTSV	2	1	0
		None	4	2	2

^aGLH fed on plants infected with RTBV and RTSV were individually given a 1-d inoculation access feeding on seedlings.

no correlation between the areas of basic honeydew spots excreted by the individual leafhoppers during inoculation feeding and life span on the same variety.

On IR54, there was no clear tendency indicating that GLH which predominantly excreted more basic honeydew transmitted the viruses at higher rate. But on IR36 and TN1, GLH which excreted more basic honeydew transmitted the viruses. Irrespective of variety, a high proportion of GLH which fed on both phloem and xylem transmitted the viruses. About one-third of the GLH that fed on xylem alone transmitted the viruses.

The results indicate that virus transmission occurs even when GLH feed predominantly on xylem.

Incidence of rice panicle stalk blast (BI) in Manipur

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Internodal culm BI of rice was found for the first time in experimental plots of MAC and in many rice-growing areas in Manipur in 1985; the incidence was severe in 1986.

Punshi and KD 2-6-3, varieties widely cultivated in Manipur, suffered 60-100% yield loss.

The disease attacked rice plants from anthesis on. Symptoms were numerous white, empty panicles. But the